

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part VII.

BY UPENDRANATH BRAHMACHARI AND JNANENDRA
MOHAN DAS-GUPTA.

In part VI of the series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 37) we described the preparation of 6-methoxy-8-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride which is structurally related to plasmoquine. It occurred to us that by ethylation we could enhance the similarity of this compound with plasmoquine and expected that they might possess some antimalarial properties. Other simpler aminoquinoline derivatives have also been synthesised with the same end in view.

Attempts to prepare the alkylated products by condensing β -bromopropylalkylamines with aminoquinolines were unsuccessful.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Methoxy-8- β -diethylaminoisopropylaminoquinoline Dihydrochloride.

6-Methoxy-8- β -aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride (3.1 g.) (*loc. cit.*) was dissolved in water (15-20 c.c.) and treated with anhydrous sodium carbonate (4 g.) when the corresponding base was precipitated as a viscous sticky mass. After the addition of a little more than the theoretical quantity of ethyl iodide the mixture was refluxed for 2½ hours on a water-bath. The alkylated product floated as an oil and was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate and a dry current of hydrochloric acid gas passed through it when the dihydrochloride was

precipitated but soon coalesced. The precipitate was next dissolved in a little absolute alcohol from which it crystallised out as a solid yellow crystalline substance readily dissolving in water to a clear yellow solution, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 11.75; Cl, 19.53. $C_{17}H_{27}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 11.66, Cl, 19.72 per cent.).

6-Methoxy-8-β-dimethylaminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride.—6-Methoxy-8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride (4.5 g.) dissolved in water (12 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath with N_2CO_3 (6 g.) and CH_3I (5.2 g.) for 2-3 hours. The dihydrochloride was prepared as before. It is a yellowish brown crystalline compound easily dissolving in water, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 12.70; Cl, 21.33. $C_{15}H_{23}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 12.65; Cl, 21.38 per cent.).

8-β-Dimethylaminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride was prepared from 8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride (*loc. cit.*). It is a yellowish brown powder, m.p. 200-205°. (Found: N, 14.04; Cl, 23.40. $C_{14}H_{21}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 13.90; Cl, 23.51 per cent.).

6-Methyl-8-β-dimethylaminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride was also prepared from 6-methyl-8-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline hydrochloride, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 13.22; Cl, 22.32. $C_{15}H_{23}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 13.29; Cl, 22.46 per cent.).

2-Methyl-6-methoxy-8-β-dimethylaminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride prepared from 2-methyl-6-methoxy-8-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride in the usual way, melts at 218°. (Found: N, 12.00; Cl, 20.33. $C_{16}H_{25}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 12.14; Cl, 20.52 per cent.).

β-Hydroxypropyl-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride.—Allyl-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride (1 g.) (*loc. cit.*) was warmed with fuming HBr (5 c.c.) on a water-bath for 15-30 minutes. Excess of HBr was partly removed on the water-bath in a basin and the cooled mixture was next made alkaline. β-Bromopropyl-8-aminoquinoline was precipitated as an oil and was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and the ether removed when an oily substance was obtained which solidified on cooling and scratching and purified from alcohol.

A mixture of β-bromopropyl-8-aminoquinoline (1.2 g.) and water (10-12 c.c.) was gently boiled with Na_2CO_3 (2 g.) for 3-4 hours and the oil that separated was extracted with ether. The hydrochloride was prepared as usual and crystallised from alcohol. It melts at 170-72°.

That it is the β -hydroxy derivative follows from the fact that it can as well be prepared by condensing chloro*is*opropyl alcohol with 8-aminoquinoline in the usual way. It is thus proved that it is the β -bromo- and β -hydroxy-compounds that are formed in the former method. (Found: N, 11.80; Cl, 15.00. $C_{12}H_{15}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 11.74, Cl, 14.88 per cent.).

6-Ethoxy- β -hydroxypropyl-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride.—6-Ethoxy-8-*n*-allylaminoquinoline hydrochloride (0.5 g.) was treated with fuming HBr (5 c.c.) and was then proceeded with as above. The hydrochloride melts at 165° and is hydrolysed by water. (Found: N, 10.02; Cl, 12.32. $C_{14}H_{19}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.91; Cl, 12.56 per cent.).

8-n-Lactylaminoquinoline hydrochloride.—8-Aminoquinoline (0.5 g.) and ethyl lactate (0.8 g.) were heated together in an oil-bath at 130° for 2½ hours. The mixture was cooled, treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and shaken with ether to remove oily insoluble matters. The aqueous solution was filtered, made alkaline and extracted with ether from which the hydrochloride was precipitated by passing dry HCl gas. It was further purified by crystallisation from alcohol. It is a light yellow crystalline powder which is hydrolysed by water, m. p. 182-85°. It also results from heating the lactate of 8-aminoquinoline at 175° for 2 hours. (Found: N, 11.21; Cl, 14.22. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.09; Cl, 14.06 per cent.).

8-n-Lactylamino-6-ethoxyquinoline hydrochloride was obtained similarly from ethyl lactate and 6-ethoxy-8-aminoquinoline. The hydrochloride which hydrolyses with water melts at 177°. (Found: N, 14.02; Cl, 18.21. $C_{14}H_{17}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 14.25; Cl, 18.06 per cent.).

THE BRAHMACHARI RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
82/3, CORNWALLIS STREET,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 27, 1932.

